

Genes related to aging and longevity: from genome to phenome

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Abstract

Aging is a complex biological process influenced by both genetic and environmental factors. At the genetic level, key genes such as *FOXO*, *SIRT1*, and *APOE* play crucial roles in longevity by regulating essential cellular processes like DNA repair, oxidative stress, and inflammation. These genes are involved in maintaining genomic stability and modulating pathways critical for aging. In parallel, epigenetic modifications, driven by environmental factors, alter gene expression without changing the underlying DNA sequence, contributing to aging variability among individuals. Furthermore, specific signaling pathways such as *IGF-1* and *mTOR* directly influence cellular growth, metabolism, and aging. The *IGF-1* pathway is associated with insulin signaling and promotes cell growth and division, while *mTOR* regulates cell growth and protein synthesis. Both pathways have been linked to aging-related diseases and lifespan regulation. Understanding the interplay between these genetic and molecular mechanisms provides valuable insights into potential anti-aging therapies aimed at slowing down the aging process, improving quality of life, and extending healthy lifespan.

Keywords: Aging, FOXO, SIRT1, APOE, epigenetics, IGF-1, mTOR, DNA repair, longevity.

1. Define Aging and Its Biological Basis

Aging is a complex, natural process characterized by the gradual decline in physiological functions and increased vulnerability to diseases. On a cellular level, aging results from the accumulation of molecular damage due to factors like oxidative stress, DNA damage, and telomere shortening. Aging genes regulate critical pathways involved in these processes, such as DNA repair, inflammation, and apoptosis. Key biological mechanisms include the *mTOR* pathway, insulin/*IGF-1* signaling, and sirtuins, all of which influence longevity and the aging process [1-3].

Aging at the cellular level is characterized by a gradual decline in structure and function over time. Primary aging includes natural processes like the loss of postmitotic cells in organs such as the brain and heart, as well as negative changes in the extracellular matrix. This type of aging is driven by the intrinsic aging process itself. In contrast, secondary aging arises from external factors such as diseases, smoking, and ultraviolet radiation exposure, which accelerate cellular and tissue deterioration [4].

Genes play a significant role in determining lifespan, as seen in the wide variation across species, from a few days to over 100 years. Primary aging is influenced by genetic mechanisms that protect cells and tissues, including DNA repair and cancer prevention.

Longer-lived species tend to have more effective systems than shorter-lived animals like rats. In humans, genetics accounts for around 35% of the variance in lifespan. While no gene has been found to slow aging in humans, certain genotypes can delay secondary aging by reducing disease risk, such as genes that protect against coronary artery disease [5] [6].

Aging genes play a crucial role in determining the lifespan of organisms by influencing cellular and molecular processes that affect longevity [1]. These genes regulate essential mechanisms such as DNA repair, oxidative stress resistance, and cell cycle control, all of which are vital for maintaining the structural and functional integrity of cells and tissues.

Mutations in key aging genes can accelerate aging or contribute to age-related diseases, while certain gene variants are linked to enhanced longevity by protecting against conditions like cancer and cardiovascular disease. Understanding these genes provides insights into potential therapeutic interventions for age-related disorders and healthy aging [7].

For example, genes like *SIRT1*, *FOXO*, and *mTOR* are known to impact lifespan by modulating cellular metabolism, stress response, and autophagy, key processes that maintain cellular health. Advances in genetic research continue to uncover how genetic and environmental interactions contribute to aging, with implications for developing anti-aging therapies [8][9].

Aging genes play a pivotal role in determining lifespan by regulating several vital cellular processes:

1. **DNA Repair:** Genes like **WRN** and **ATM** maintain genomic integrity by repairing DNA damage. Ineffective repair leads to mutations, accelerating aging and diseases like cancer.
2. **Inflammation:** Genes like **NF-κB** control inflammatory pathways. Chronic low-grade inflammation, termed "inflammaging," promotes tissue damage and aging-related disorders.
3. **Oxidative Stress:** Genes such as **SOD2** manage antioxidant defenses. Increased ROS damages proteins, lipids, and DNA, contributing to cellular senescence and aging.

Over time, diminished capacity for DNA repair, increased inflammation, and oxidative damage accelerate the aging process.

Recent studies highlight genetic pathways, such as **FOXO** and **mTOR**, as key regulators in extending lifespan through better stress resistance and metabolic control [10].

EXAMPLES OF PRIMARY AGING

Primary aging refers to the natural, gradual decline in physiological functions in healthy individuals over time, without the influence of disease. It leads to reductions in various capacities, including maximal oxygen uptake (Vo₂max), cardiovascular function, muscle mass, and strength. It also results in decreases in memory, reaction time, skin and lung elasticity, and conditions like presbyopia and presbycusis (age-related hearing and vision loss). As Vo₂max decreases with age, this often impacts activities such as running and even daily tasks, especially in frail older adults.

As individuals age, there is a progressive reduction in fat-free mass, primarily due to the loss of muscle and bone tissue. Although the rate of decline is similar for both genders, men start with higher muscle mass and thus experience frailty later in life. In some societies, this decrease in lean mass is masked by fat gain, but in others, body weight decreases with aging. Research by Lexell et al. revealed that a significant portion of muscle loss is attributed to a decline in muscle fibers, an irreversible process [11].

Molecular Mechanisms of Aging

For most humans, the genetic contribution to aging is relatively limited, with studies on twins and founder populations showing that genetics account for only about 20–30% of lifespan variability [12] [13]. However, at the extreme ends of the age spectrum, genetic factors may play a more significant role. Those who achieve exceptional longevity may carry rare genetic variants that contribute to their extended lifespan [14] [15]. Despite this, no single genetic or molecular mechanism can fully explain the gradual decline in physiological stability, known as homeostenosis, that occurs with aging.

A variety of interconnected molecular and cellular processes take place during normal aging, and these processes tend to accelerate in cases of premature or rapid aging. Fortunately, some of these mechanisms can be targeted to potentially extend lifespan.

López-Otín and colleagues identified nine key "hallmarks of aging" that form the foundation of our understanding of the biological mechanisms driving aging. These hallmarks include genomic instability, telomere shortening, epigenetic changes, loss of proteostasis, dysregulated nutrient sensing, mitochondrial dysfunction, cellular senescence, stem cell exhaustion, and impaired intercellular communication [1].

Many of these hallmarks offer promising therapeutic targets to address age-related functional decline and improve physiological stability. However, it's important to note that potential interventions are not without risks. As we delve deeper into the mechanisms of aging, measuring these hallmarks through biological markers becomes crucial for developing a comprehensive biological age score (BAS), which reflects the molecular underpinnings of aging and provides a more accurate picture of an individual's biological rather than chronological age.

Epigenetic

Epigenetic alterations, which involve heritable changes in phenotype without mutations in the DNA sequence, play a significant role in aging by affecting cellular function [16]. With age, there is a global loss and redistribution of heterochromatin, leading to increased transcriptional noise [17] [18]. Specific changes include increases in H4K16 acetylation and H4K20/H3K4 trimethylation, and decreases in H3K9/H3K27 methylation [19].

Studies have shown that lifespan can be extended by deleting the H3K4 and H3K27 methylation complexes in worms and flies [20] [21]. The role of DNA methylation in aging remains less clear, showing gene-activating hypomethylation with age but also hypermethylation at tumor suppressor gene loci [22].

Large-scale analyses have identified an "epigenetic clock," which correlates closely with healthy aging [23]. Unlike many aging mechanisms, epigenetic changes are potentially reversible, offering promising therapeutic targets. Drugs such as DNA methyltransferase and histone deacetylase inhibitors show potential for promoting healthy aging, but more precise targeting is needed to minimize side effects, including unintended immune responses [24].

Proteostasis:

Protein homeostasis, or proteostasis, becomes compromised with age, but maintaining proteostasis can preserve the integrity of the proteome and delay aging in mammals [25] [26]. The two primary pathways for protein quality control—the autophagy-lysosomal system and the ubiquitin-proteasome system—experience reduced functionality as aging progresses [27] [28]. Targeting these systems to enhance proteostasis is a potential therapeutic approach for promoting healthy aging [27].

Research has shown that deubiquitylase inhibitors and proteasome activators help clear harmful proteins in human cells [28]. However, proteasome activators, as characterized by Lee et al., exhibited toxicity in a dose-dependent manner, leading to cell hypoproliferation, indicating that further refinement of these therapies is necessary to reduce adverse effects.

The influence of pathways on the aging process:

Pathways like **IGF-1** and **mTOR** play central roles in regulating aging by controlling processes like cell growth, metabolism, and stress resistance:

IGF-1 Pathway: Insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) is involved in promoting growth and development. Reduced IGF-1 signaling has been linked to extended lifespan in multiple organisms, including worms, flies, and mammals. Lower IGF-1 activity enhances stress resistance and lowers cancer risk by reducing cell proliferation, which slows aging [29-31].

mTOR Pathway: The mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR) regulates cell growth, metabolism, and protein synthesis. Inhibition of mTOR, such as through dietary restriction or drugs like **rapamycin**, has been shown to extend lifespan by promoting autophagy (cellular cleanup processes) and reducing the risks of age-related diseases like cancer and neurodegeneration [32-35].

Both pathways are nutrient-sensing, meaning that they respond to changes in energy availability, linking metabolism directly to the aging process. Suppressing these pathways enhances stress resistance and longevity, supporting the idea that reduced nutrient signaling correlates with longer life [32-35].

AMPK Pathway: The AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) pathway is crucial for energy balance and stress response. Activation of AMPK increases longevity by promoting autophagy and improving mitochondrial function. It helps maintain cellular energy by inhibiting anabolic processes like protein synthesis and activating catabolic processes that generate ATP [35-39].

Sirtuin Pathway (SIRT): Sirtuins are NAD⁺-dependent enzymes that regulate metabolic function, DNA repair, and gene expression. Increased sirtuin activity promotes longevity by enhancing stress resistance and regulating apoptosis [39-43].

FOXO Pathway: FOXO transcription factors are key downstream regulators of the insulin/IGF-1 pathway, promoting longevity through the activation of genes involved in stress resistance, DNA repair, and metabolism [44-47].

p53 Pathway: p53 controls DNA damage responses and apoptosis. Dysregulation of p53 can lead to cellular senescence or cancer. Proper functioning helps protect against aging by preventing the accumulation of DNA damage [48-51].

The phenome in aging gene:

The phenome in aging gene research refers to the collection of observable traits and biological processes associated with

aging, influenced by genetic factors and environmental interactions. This includes variations in lifespan, age-related diseases, and functional declines, such as reduced muscle strength and cognitive impairments. Key aging genes, like FOXO and SIRT1, play roles in these phenotypic expressions by regulating cellular mechanisms, including DNA repair and oxidative stress responses. Understanding the aging phenome is crucial for developing interventions to promote healthy aging and longevity [52] [53].

This involves examining the observable traits that result from genetic interactions influencing aging. This includes lifespan variations, physical and cognitive declines, and age-related diseases. For example, genes like **FOXO3** have been shown to affect longevity by regulating stress resistance and metabolism, while **SIRT1** promotes DNA repair and cell survival. In mice, suppression of **mTOR** signaling leads to extended lifespan, demonstrating the phenotypic effect of gene manipulation on aging. Understanding these traits offers insight into healthy aging interventions [54-56].

The genome in aging gene:

Until now, many studies have been conducted in the field of finding genes related to aging and their role in the cell. Here are examples of them (Table 1):

FOXO3:

The FOXO3 gene is crucial for longevity and stress resistance. It regulates various cellular processes, including apoptosis and DNA repair, contributing to lifespan extension. Studies indicate that certain variants of FOXO3 are associated with increased longevity in humans, suggesting its protective role against age-related diseases [57].

SIRT1:

SIRT1 is a member of the sirtuin family, which plays a significant role in regulating cellular processes related to aging, such as metabolism, inflammation, and stress resistance. SIRT1 activation has been shown to promote longevity in various organisms and may protect against age-related diseases through its influence on mitochondrial function [58].

APOE:

The APOE gene encodes apolipoprotein E, which is involved in lipid metabolism and is linked to neurodegenerative diseases. Specific alleles, particularly APOE ε4, are associated with a higher risk of Alzheimer's disease, while the ε2 allele is linked to increased longevity, highlighting the gene's role in aging and disease susceptibility [59].

TP53:

TP53 is a tumor suppressor gene that plays a critical role in cellular stress responses, including DNA repair and apoptosis. Its activity helps prevent the accumulation of damaged cells, thereby contributing to longevity. Dysregulation of TP53 can lead to increased cancer risk and aging-related diseases [60].

mTOR:

The mTOR pathway is a central regulator of cell growth and metabolism, influencing lifespan and aging. Inhibition of mTOR signaling has been associated with increased lifespan in several model organisms. This pathway is critical for responding to nutrient availability and is involved in age-related diseases [61].

IGF-1R:

The insulin-like growth factor 1 receptor (IGF-1R) pathway is involved in growth and development, influencing aging processes. Reduced signaling through IGF-1R has been linked to increased lifespan in various species. Genetic variations in this pathway may affect susceptibility to age-related diseases [62].

KLOTHO:

KLOTHO is a gene associated with longevity and age-related disorders. It encodes a protein that regulates mineral metabolism and has neuroprotective effects. Higher KLOTHO levels are linked to enhanced cognitive function and reduced risk of age-related diseases [63].

NAD+:

NAD+ is a coenzyme involved in metabolic processes and is crucial for cellular energy production. Its levels decline with age, impacting mitochondrial function and promoting age-related diseases. Supplementing NAD+ precursors has shown promise in enhancing healthspan and lifespan in preclinical studies [64].

Table 1: we briefly mention the genes and their role in the aging process

Gene Name	Role in the aging process	reference
FOXO3	Involved in stress resistance and longevity.	57
SIRT1	Regulates cellular metabolism and DNA repair	58
APOE	Linked to cholesterol metabolism and Alzheimer's disease risk	59
TP53	Plays a role in cell cycle regulation and apoptosis	60
mTOR	Involved in cell growth and metabolism; regulates lifespan	61
IGF-1R	Influences growth factors related to longevity	62
KLOTHO	Associated with longevity and mineral metabolism	63
NAD+	Affects energy metabolism and cellular health	64

4. Conclusion

Aging is a complex biological process characterized by a gradual decline in cellular function and increased susceptibility to diseases. Aging genes, such as FOXO, SIRT1, and APOE, play pivotal roles in lifespan determination by regulating critical cellular processes like DNA repair, inflammation, and oxidative stress. Environmental factors also modify gene expression via epigenetic mechanisms, which influence aging without altering DNA sequences. Pathways like IGF-1 and mTOR are key regulators of aging, influencing cellular growth, metabolism, and stress responses. Understanding these genes and pathways offers

potential for therapeutic interventions aimed at promoting healthy aging and longevity.

In conclusion, the exploration of aging genes and their associated pathways, such as IGF-1, mTOR, AMPK, Sirtuins, and FOXO, underscores their crucial role in regulating lifespan and mitigating cellular damage. These pathways interact to manage key processes, including DNA repair, oxidative stress reduction, and inflammation control, which are essential for healthy aging. Ongoing research into these molecular mechanisms provides valuable insights into potential anti-aging therapies, offering hope for interventions that can extend longevity and combat age-related diseases by modulating these genetic pathways.

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